

Original Research

The Contribution of Digital Credit Uprising on Banking Performance in Tanzania: A Case of NMB Agency in Dodoma City

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Abstract

As digital technology continues transforming the banking sector, the digital credit revolution is also becoming attractive in Africa and worldwide. Digital credit is a service that provides instant short-term loans offered via mobile money, especially in the banking industry. In Tanzania, few studies have assessed its contributions to commercial banking performances. This study intends to evaluate the contributions of the digital credit uprising on banking performance in Tanzania, focusing on the NMB Agency in Dodoma City. Specifically, the study intends to assess the role of NMB digital credit platforms on bank performance; and examine the limiting factors hindering digital credit platforms' performance in the banking industry. Data were collected through surveys and interview methods and analyzed using multiple regression and content analysis. The study found a significant relationship between the presence of digital credit platforms and bank performance. However, the findings reveal that low customer awareness was a major limiting factor hindering NMB digital credit performance in the study area. The study concludes that NMB digital credit platforms, digital credit accessibility, and time for loan processing are key determinants of the digital credit uprising at NMB for the bank's performance in Dodoma City. The study recommends collaborative efforts between government and private sectors in regulating cyber security to enhance banking performance.

Keywords: Banking Performance, Digital Credit, Digital Loan, Digital Technology, Digital Transformation.

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Introduction

Globally, the banking sector is transforming due to the growth of digital technology whereas mobile technology and digital lending platforms are gaining attraction. The traditional banking system which was characterized by limited financial accessibility and inclusion is currently changing through the mobile technology and the development of fintech companies. Globally, the digital credit revolution is becoming attractive due to its remote nature, instant accessibility, and automated identity protection (Momanyi, 2021). Although digital credit revolutions come with challenges like cyberattacks, their potential should not be undermined. It is articulated that, Asia is at the forefront of the digital credit revolution, which promises a radical transformation of the global economy, and indeed of society itself, while at the same time threatening substantial disruptions and dislocation (Sedik, 2019). The digital revolution brings immense potential to improve social and economic outcomes and enhance productivity growth and population well-being globally (Wajcman *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, it is reported that globally 1.7 billion adults still lack access to formal financial services, with a large percentage (over 75% of the adult population) living in the developing world such as South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa (Cull, *et al.*, 2018).

Digital credit has expanded rapidly in Africa whereby mostly provided in the form of short-term with interest loans which are offered via mobile money, especially in the banking industry (Moini, 2019). For example, data shows that in Sub-Saharan Africa less than half of the population had a bank account in 2017. This data indicates the low global bank account ownership target of 69% (World Bank 2018); a situation which hinders access to loan services among bank customers. Also, loan terms are often opaque and consumer financial literacy is low, providing opportunities for predatory lending (Brailovskaya *et al.*, 2021). It is also reported that nearly 300 million Africans live more than 50 km from a fiber or cable broadband connection, hence the lack of widespread availability of high-speed (broadband) internet remains a significant hurdle for Africa to fully harness the full potential of digital transformation (CGAP, 2017). Mobile devices remain the primary way by which people access the internet today, and dedicated internet connections to homes and offices (such as with fiber-to-the-premise) are mostly absent, except in some capital cities (Smit *et al.*, 2019).

In Sub-Saharan Africa, the introduction of mobile banking services such as M-shwari, Mpesa, Tigo Pesa, and Airtel money, to mention a few, has become an integral part of the financial ecosystem, especially in terms of access to financial services such as credits and gave rise to the digital credit services among financial institutions. Digital credit has also expanded dramatically primarily via bank-telecom partnerships that leverage existing well-developed mobile money infrastructure in these regions (Masolo & Wanjohi, 2021). For example, in Kenya M-Shwari is arguably known as the best and the most prominent telecom digital credit product with a partnership between Safaricom and the Commercial Bank of Africa. The telecom is reported to have 4 million monthly active users in 2020-21 and making about 17 million loans (Masolo & Wanjohi, 2021). Save (2019) reports that in 2018 there were 10 digital loans for every traditional loan in Kenya. In the past several years, digital credit has rapidly proliferated in Sub-Saharan Africa, yet there is

virtually no quantitative research to examine its effects on banking performances (Kamau, 2021) a gap that this research finds reasonably important to fill.

In Tanzania, the digital credit revolution is well-argued as the supportive alternative to the number of constraints facing bank customers in the country and elsewhere (World Bank Group, 2021). The digital credit revolution first emerged in the country just five years ago, when Vodacom launched M-Pawa, in cooperation with the Commercial Bank of Africa, then continues to grow rapidly. There are now four digital credit providers with over 5 million loan accounts in the country (Izaguirre et al., 2018). The rise of digital credit in Tanzania has generated excitement among many commercial banks including NMB Bank, which looks it as a way to extend credit to low-income segments in hard-to-serve areas where bank branches are not established (Izaguirre *et al.*, 2018). The situation calls upon NMB Bank to continue to innovate and offer its customers a richer, better connected, and more exciting personal experience using the rapidly growing digital technology. NMB bank trusts that with digital technology, including the digital credit revolution the bank can have a fantastic opportunity to develop quality online services (NMB Annual Report, 2020).

Studies reveal that despite that digital credit has expanded rapidly in both Kenya and Tanzania, there is limited evidence on how it is used, and the risks that customers face (Kaffenberger *et al.*, 2018; Totolo, 2018) as a cornerstone to understanding its contribution on achieving banking performance. However, it has been asserted that digital credit has been in Tanzania for years, but still there have been few analyses of the country's digital credit in relation to the performance of commercial banks especially the NMB bank (Kaffenberger *et al.*, 2018). For example, for the past few years in Tanzania, the digital credit revolution has emerged as an alternative mechanism for providing short-term loans (Francis *et al.*, 2017). Data shows that about 21% of Tanzanians have used digital credit services whereas urban men reveal as the biggest users (Izaguirre *et al.*, 2018). Also, data shows that just above half (54%) of Tanzanians who used digital credits in 2018 had a digital credit outstanding and two-thirds of digital borrowers had taken out at least one loan in the past 90 days (Kaffenberger *et al.*, 2018) which raise a concern on banking performance. While the existing studies raise important concerns about digital credit's impact on customers (Izaguirre *et al.*, 2018; Kaffenberger, 2018); very little is known about the digital credit revolution on banking performances. The contribution of digital credits on bank performance remains largely unknown in Tanzania and beyond since this uprising is a new banking practice in the study area. To add up, the issue of defaults for digital borrowers in commercial banks such as NMB bank is alarming with unknown reasons behind the situation. Therefore, this calls upon the investigation of the contribution of the digital credit uprising on banking performance using a case of the NMB agency in Dodoma City. Specifically, the study focuses on the two objectives. First, is to assess the role played by NMB digital credit platforms on bank performance; and second is to examine the limiting factors hindering digital credit platforms' performance in the banking industry.

Literature Reviews

Digital Credit Revolution

Understanding “digital credit” is key for this study, however, the conceptualization of the term “digital” changes or transformation is also important for understanding the perspective of digital credit. The current digital transformation happening in the banking sector reflects the use of digital technology in service provision to bank customers. In the banking sector digital banking depicts the use of digital devices (electronic) and telecommunication network technology such as e-banking in providing banking services. Scholars refer digital credit as the application of advanced technologies on loan accessibility which reaches millions of borrowers through the use of digital channels (e.g. mobile phones or the internet) without the involvement of a salesperson (Kaffenberger et al., 2018; Totolo, 2018). This conceptualization is built on the infrastructure of mobile money, specifically a mobile financial service (MFS) that enables mobile phone users to transfer money via ubiquitous mobile networks. On the other hand, scholars note that digital credit encompasses multiple dimensions, distinguishing itself from other related digital lending models, such as digital peer-to-peer lending, in which peers (not algorithms) assess creditworthiness (Johnen et al 2021:3)). This is regarded as a new revolution in the banking sector where the lending of credits is done digitally through the use of mobile technology. This study understands digital credits as the application of digital technology in providing the loan that entirely uses mobile devices in delivering the loan, provided that there is a mobile network.

Banking performance

Banking performance has been regarded as a crucial factor in the banking industry. It is defined as the main driver of profitability generated from their operations (Trung, 2022) and measured by return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). Other scholars regard banking performance in terms of improving bank operations, market position, and competitive advantages (Chai et al., 2016). It can be argued that the efficiency and effectiveness of banking services are improved, as technology advances, thus improving banking performance. From the perspective of this study, digital credits are anticipated to relate to banking performance. This study regards banking performance in terms of utilizing digital technology in credit delivery using mobile devices that aim to provide instance banking services and enhance customer interaction.

Theoretical Literature Review

This study is guided by the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) developed by Everett Rodgers 1962 (Dearing & Cox, 2018). The theory outlines how new technologies, such as digital credit as per this study, and other related advancements can spread throughout and support performance of the banking activities (Dearing & Cox, 2018). The theory also argues how the innovation of a product or idea diffuses over time to a particular population. It posits that the adoption of innovations occurs through a process involving several key elements such as: the innovation itself, communication channels, social systems, the time factor, and the perceived attributes of the innovation. This innovation process is key in diffusing technology across society from time to time, although, the

nature or characteristics of innovation determine the successful use of technology (Syahadiyanti & Subriadi, 2018). Moreover, the theory suggests five (5) innovation characteristics, namely: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability which all together as innovative components enhance the spread of technology. These variables are key to the spread of digital credit technology adoption among bank customers. For this study, the Diffusion and Innovation theory perspective helps identify the factors influencing the uptake of digital credit services among bank customers. Additionally, the theory gives a wide chance to explain in detail digital technology and changes in people's behavior in almost every aspect of life such as e-commerce, digital social interactions, public transportation, and financial technology (Rogers *et al.*, 2014). Such behavior changes in technology use among bank customers contribute to improved banking performance. Further, the theory entails that utilization of digital information technology helps people, companies, and the banking industry in running the economy more effective and efficient (Ramavhona & Mokwena, 2016).

However, even though the theory contains great potentiality in technology and innovation including the use of digital credit systems, its weaknesses include being less accurate in predicting the acceptance of online financial practices by consumers though argued that only three variables (relative advantage, compatibility, and complexity) of the theory are proven to affect the acceptance of online financial practices (Kapoor *et al.*, 2013; Gounaris & Koritos, 2008). In addition to that the theory doesn't consider an individual's resources or social support to adopt the new behavior (or innovation). In this study, the diffusion of innovation theory is applicable since it gives room to describe how innovations are applied in the banking system and the time it takes for technology to spread for improved customer services and therefore boost banking performance. The theory can be linked to this study in the perspectives of innovation as a determinant factor of the successful use of digital credit technology in the bank industry which is also applied in the study area.

Empirical Literature Review

Digital credit platforms and banking performance

Currently, “the banking sector is one of the most important sectors that introduce and use the latest achievements in the field of information and communication technologies” (Koroleva and Kudryavtseva (2020:325). A digital credit platform is a system that provides users the opportunity to integrate digital systems such as customer credit management in the banking sector. Some scholars regard digital credit as a new lending practice facilitated by online platforms rather than traditional banks or lending companies (Cornelli *et al.*, 2023). However, Wardrop *et al.*, (2015) refer digital credit to as “debt-based alternative finance”, while others refer to “fintech lending”, or “fintech credit” (Cornelli *et al.*, 2023). Digital platforms can perform multiple functions, two core functionalities can be identified consistent with the role of platforms in ‘bridging’ customers and the providers of financial (and non-financial) products and services: improving the visibility of products and services (i.e. marketing); facilitating the conclusion of contracts for products and services, whether directly or by ‘funneling’ customers to the website of the relevant product or service provider (EBA, 2021). This new lending practice through technology implicates banking performance in terms of

customer services and the operation of banking credit activities. A practical example of digital credit practices is conducted in Kenya by Masolo and Wanjohi (2021) on digital credit and financial performance of the selected commercial banks, applied descriptive statistics and panel multiple regression analysis, revealed a positive and significant relationship between the independent variables (mobile network operator-based loans, website-based loans, and app-based loans) and financial performance from selected commercial banks. The regression analysis also revealed a positive significant relationship between independent variables (mobile network operator-based loans and website-based loans) and financial performance while app-based loans did not show a significant relationship. Additionally, other experts conducted a study in Tanzania on the effect of electronic banking on commercial banks' financial performance (Maseko and Kalma, 2022). The study applied a case study design and quantitative approaches. The study used questionnaires to collect data that were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression. Results showed that customers utilized four electronic banking products ATMs, Agency banking, mobile banking, and online banking whereby all products were found statistically significant. The study also revealed the relevance of Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) in explaining bank profitability. Therefore, the study concluded a positive correlation between e-banking and the banks' profit.

Hindrance of digital credit in the banking industry

As digital credit is gaining pace globally in the digital era, some scholars have embarked to research the hindrance factors for this uptake. Rahman and Islam (2020) conducted a study in Greece on the rapid risk growth in using digital banking. The study found that bank deposits are not insured, however, the government intervenes to ensure that depositors do not suffer a loss. The findings also indicate that despite the rapid growth of digital banking globally, very few countries have insurance in practice to cover digital-transaction including digital credit. Banks face serious pitfalls and risks when using digital credit services. The study however indicated that customers do not read the terms and conditions of bank digital credit services, these weaknesses cause abuses and thus hinder bank performances.

In addressing the challenges for digital credit, a report prepared by Ogada and Hammond (2021) on the digital credit landscape based in India, Nigeria, and Kenya revealed that digital credit annual percentage rates can be very high despite the low overhead costs compared to traditional loan providers. The report outlined a variety of drivers of the high cost including the concern that providers are not subjected to interest rate caps that constrain traditional loans; providers can face pressure for quick profits from their investors; a high default risk requiring high interest rates in return; revenue sharing arrangements within partnerships can drive up costs; and administrative and data sourcing costs can still be high. The report also argues that while cost is important, consumers are often as or more concerned with other factors such as access, convenience, amount, and comfort. The report evidenced that, consumers also struggle to understand and compare product costs effectively. Also, according to Totolo (2018), almost half of digital borrowers reported having been late in repaying the loan, whereby late repayment is slightly more common among men. In this case, the report notes that these challenges for digital credits hinder the performance of the banking industry in Kenya. A study on the digital credit revolution focused on insights from borrowers in Kenya and Tanzania

by (Kaffenberger *et al.*, 2018) reveals that general consumer protection regulation applied to digital credit products still faces challenges relating to rules and regulations. For example, some of the rules do not apply to non-regulated digital credit products, including those from app-based and “over-the-top” lenders; or from partnerships between Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) and unregulated lenders. This results in an uneven playing field, where regulated and unregulated lenders operate under different rules. The study also indicates that about 27% of digital borrowers in Tanzania and 19% in Kenya reported experiencing at least one form of poor transparency in digital credits. These include unexpected fees, unexpected withdrawal by lenders, or not understanding the costs or terms of the loan. These challenges attract customer complaints and thus affect bank performance from the technology point of view.

Research Methodology

This study employed a concurrent mixed research approach involving quantitative and qualitative research approaches. Qualitative and quantitative data were both collected simultaneously and thereafter were analyzed separately. The choice of a mixed research approach is motivated by its ability to capture much data with minimal time (Palacios, 2014). This study employed a descriptive research design that collected quantifiable information for statistical analysis of the sampled population. The motives of using this research design include portraying accurately the characteristics of a particular group or situation, and describing phenomena as they exist. The study’s target population was 406 including all NMB Agencies who use NMB digital credit services in Dodoma city. Also, the study targeted key informants who included 5 branch managers and 5 loan officers identified from the five (5) selected NMB branches namely Bunge, Makole, Mazengo, Dodoma, and Kambarage located in Dodoma city. The sample size of 81 NMB agencies in Dodoma City was determined using the Yamane formula (Yamane, 1967). Moreover, the formula provides the degree of accuracy of the sampling technique. The formula applied is $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ where n - represents sample size, N - represents the total population, and e - represents a margin of error limit. Therefore $n = \frac{406}{1 + 406(0.01)^2} = 80.23 \approx 81$.

The study employed both probability and non-probability sampling whereas, purposive sampling was employed for non-probability sampling and simple random sampling was employed for probability sampling. Purposive sampling was used to select key informants (KIs) including NMB branch managers and NMB loan officers. These key informants were selected based on their experience in handling digital credits and their specialized knowledge in loan processing, therefore, have potential knowledge and information about the study topic. We acknowledge that non-probability sampling may introduce certain limitations, such as potential biases in self-reported data, and these have been considered in our analysis. However, simple random sampling was used to obtain 81 NMB Agencies from five selected NMB branches operating in Dodoma City.

The study involved survey and interview data collection methods. The survey method was used to collect data on the role of digital credit platforms on bank performance at NMB. Both open and closed-ended questions were used in the questionnaire. Five (5) Point Likert Scale questions were used to capture participants' responses on the subject matter. The survey was applied because it enhanced data collection from a large number

of respondents. Furthermore; the study employed structured interview questions to understand the limiting factors hindering digital credit platforms' performance in the banking industry. The interview method was regarded as necessary since it enhanced the collection of respondents' views and perceptions (Kothari *et al*, 2014) regarding the limiting factors that hinder the digital credits for bank performance. Interview guide questions were administered to key informants including 5 (five) NMB branch managers and 5 (five) NMB loan officers in Dodoma City. In this study, the key informant is considered as an individual who is experienced in managing digital credits in NMB Bank and has greater knowledge and skills based on digital credits in NMB Bank. The interview method is designed to get detailed information, views, and opinions from the key informants (Kothari *et al*, 2014). Data were analyzed both qualitatively and quantitatively. Quantitative data were used to analyze the role played by digital credit platforms on bank performance. A multiple regression model was employed by using the equation below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \dots + \epsilon$$

Where:

- Y= banking performance
- β_0 is the intercept term
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and β_4 are the regression coefficients for digital credit accessibility, digital credit platform, time for loan processing loan cost, and consumer worthiness respectively
- $X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4,$ and X_5 are variables representing digital credit accessibility, digital credit platform, time for loan processing, loan cost, and consumer worthiness respectively
- ϵ is the error term

In qualitative data, the content analysis technique was used to examine the limiting factors hindering the performance of digital credit platforms in the banking industry. Steps were followed as referred to by Vears *et al*. (2020) these include deciding the level of analysis, the number of concepts to code, coding the test, and finally analyzing results. The qualitative data was summarized, analyzed, and presented using textual representation (quotes) after organizing them into patterns based on research objectives.

With regard to adherence of ethical considerations, maintained the participant anonymity and data confidentiality. In protecting the participant's anonymity researchers ensured that no identifying information could be linked to the data to safeguard personal information. Also, in protecting data confidentiality the secured data storage and control data access such as file encryption were adhered. These protections enhance the credibility of the research findings and reduce privacy concerns from participants. On the other hand, the participants' consent was sought, and were given the freedom to withdraw at any time they wished during the data collection period. This adherence reinforces the validity and reliability of the study outcomes.

In testing the study reliability to measure the degree to which an assessment tool produces stable (error-free) and consistent results, Cronbach’s Alpha was applied. In this matter, a few questions under Likert scales were arranged to test the reliability of the two variables; digital credit accessibility and digital credit platform. Thus, just a few NMB Agencies from the study area were requested to answer the questions. The results were coded and tested for Cronbach’s Alpha using SPSS version 25.0 the results show a Cronbach’s Alpha value of more than 0.70 as indicated in Table 1 below. The St Clair-Thompson et al., 2015 noted that for a construct to be considered consistent a Cronbach’s Alpha value should be 0.70 or above.

Table 1. Reliability Test

Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient
Digital credit accessibility	4	0.753
Digital credit platform	3	0.786

Source: Few selected NMB agencies from the study area (2023).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion of the study findings as follows:

Extent to which the Digital Credit Uprising Supports Loan Accessibility in the Banking Industry

The study sought to establish the extent of the digital credit revolution to support loan accessibility in the banking industry. Respondents were asked to rate their level of agreement on the extent to which the digital credit uprising supports loan accessibility in the banking industry using a scale of 1 to 5. The study revealed that increased loan accessibility; easily accessible loans; reduced bureaucracy, and corruption on loan access are found to be agreed upon by most users as shown in Table .

Table 1. The extent to which the Digital Credit Uprising supports Loan Accessibility in Banking Industry

Variables	SA	A	N	D	SD
Easily access loans	26.3%	50%	10.5%	10.5%	2.6%
Reduces bureaucracy and corruption on loan access	31.6%	50%	13.2%	5.3%	0.0%
Timely loan access	7.9%	28.9%	26.3%	15.8%	21.1%
Increased loan access	19.3%	56.1%	12.3%	10.5%	1.8%

Note: SA=Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, N= neither Agree nor Disagree,A= Agree, SA= Strongly Agree

The extent to which the Digital Credit Revolution increases loan Accessibility in the Banking Industry

The finding in Table 1 above revealed that the majority (56.1%) of respondents agree that, the digital credit revolution supports loan accessibility in the banking industry since

it increases loan accessibility. This implies that the digital credit revolution has significantly increased loan access by leveraging mobile technology and data analytics, making it easier for individuals in underserved regions to obtain credit remotely. According to Momanyi, (2021), digital credit platforms in developing countries have expanded access to financial services by using alternative credit scoring models, such as analyzing mobile phone usage and transaction data, thereby enabling previously excluded populations to qualify for loans.

The extent to which the Digital Credit Uprising provides Easily access loans in the Banking Industry

Findings in Table 1 disclose that the majority of respondents (50%) agree that, the digital credit uprising supports loan accessibility in the banking industry since enables the agency to easily access loans. The findings imply that the digital credit revolution has significantly bolstered loan accessibility in the banking industry by democratizing financial services and expanding the reach of lenders to previously underserved populations. As noted by the World Bank (2018), digital credit platforms, often accessible through mobile devices, have enabled millions of unbanked and under-banked individuals to establish creditworthiness and access loans, thus breaking down traditional barriers such as geographical distance and lack of collateral. This transformation has, not only increased financial inclusion but also reduced the cost of loan origination and servicing, making small loans economically viable for banks and borrowers alike. It also fosters greater economic growth and stability in various regions.

The extent to which the Digital Credit Uprising Reduces bureaucracy and corruption in loan access in the Banking Industry

Moreover, the findings in Table 1 above reveal that the majority of respondents (50%) agree that the digital credit revolution supports loan accessibility in the banking industry by reducing bureaucracy and corruption on loan access. World Bank, (2020) reported that digital lending platforms have eliminated the need for extensive paperwork and manual verifications, expediting loan approvals and disbursements. Additionally, the transparency and traceability inherent in digital transactions reduce opportunities for corrupt practices, ultimately fostering a more efficient and equitable financial ecosystem (Feyen et al., 2023).

Role of NMB Digital Credit on Bank Performance

In examining the role of NMB digital credits on Bank performance, findings show that Digital Credit has contributed to banks' profit margin on aspects of digital credit accessibility, digital credit platform, and time for loan processing as indicated in the table 2.

Table 2. Regression Results on the role of NMB Digital credit on bank performance

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
(Constant)	1.002	0.009	0.000	0.000
Digital credit accessibility	0.206	0.021	1.796	0.010
Digital credit platform	0.711	0.032	2.217	0.006
Time of loan processing	0.125	0.053	3.455	0.023
Loan cost	0.241	0.094	2.620	0.140
Consumer worthiness	0.165	0.107	7.016	0.103
Dependent Variable: Profit margin $R^2= 77\%$, $F= 94.5$				

Table 2 above presents the multiple regression results that were conducted to determine the role of NMB digital credit on bank performance. In the interpretations of the multiple regression analysis, the higher value of R^2 indicates that a large proportion of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables included in the model. The results indicate that the R^2 is 0.945, meaning that 94.5% of the total variance in the dependent variable (profit margin) is accounted for by the independent variables (digital credit accessibility; digital credit platform; and time for loan processing). The higher value of R^2 indicates that the model has a good predictive accuracy of the data; and that the model is fit to explain the effects of digital credit on bank performance. From these results, the two constructs of NMB digital credit were important in influencing bank performance in the context of profit margin.

Also, the regression results in Table 2 above indicate that the relationship between NMB digital credit platforms and bank performance is positive and significant (beta=0.711, p value= 0.006). These results imply that when NMB bank improves the digital credit platform by 1 unit it leads to an increase in profit margin by 71.1%. A growing body of research supports the assertion that digital credit platforms have a positive and significant relationship with bank performance. For instance, a study by Malafronte and Zinna (2020) found that the adoption of digital credit technologies can enhance banks' operational efficiency by streamlining the loan origination process and reducing overhead costs associated with traditional lending. Furthermore, research by Abou-El-Sood et al. (2019) suggests that digital credit platforms can expand financial inclusion by reaching underserved populations, thereby increasing a bank's customer base and revenue streams. These findings underscore the transformative potential of digital credit platforms in bolstering bank performance.

Furthermore, the regression results in Table 2 above indicate that digital credit accessibility has a positive and significant (Beta=0.206, p value= 0.010) profit margin. These results imply that when NMB bank improves digital credit accessibility by 1 unit it could lead to a 21% increase in profit margin. The findings are supported by Johnen *et al.*, (2021) that investing in income-generating activities ultimately leads to higher profits. Additionally, a report by Robinson et al., (2023) highlights how digital credit can enhance working capital management, reduce borrowing costs, and improve cash flow, all of which contribute to improved profit margins. In summary, the availability of digital credit

not only empowers businesses with the capital needed for growth but also optimizes financial operations, thus resulting in higher profitability.

Additionally, the regression results in Table 2 indicate that time for loan processing has a positive and significant (Beta=0. 0.125, p value= 0.023) profit margin. These results imply that 1 unit of improving the time for loan processing on NMB Digital credit could lead to a 13% increase in profit margin. The study findings also supported by Johnen *et al.*, (2021) noted that faster loan processing improves customer satisfaction, making the bank more attractive to borrowers. Customers appreciate the convenience and efficiency of digital credit platforms, leading to higher customer retention and potentially attracting new clients. Also, Momanyi, (2021:1) supports that “digital credit is becoming popular because of its remote, instant and automated protection against the traditional consumer and microenterprise credit models”. The instant nature of digital credit increases customer satisfaction thus enhancing bank performance. On the other hand, speedy loan processing allows banks to monitor their loan portfolios more effectively. They can quickly identify and address potential issues, such as delinquencies or defaults, reducing credit risk and enhancing overall asset quality. However, insufficient access to the network implicates the timely disbursement of loans Griffith-Jones *et al.*, (2020) which impacts customer satisfaction and bank performance.

Limiting Factors Hindering the Performance of Digital Credit Platforms in Banking Industry

When assessing the limiting factors hindering digital credit platforms' performance for the Banking industry in the study area, key informants reveal the following factors:

Insufficient access to networks

The study findings highlighted network accessibility as a challenge that hinders the performance of digital credit platforms in the banking industry. It was found that poor networks on both the Bank system and mobile network were not strong enough to facilitate credit applications to consumers thus implicating their performance as illustrated below:

“The poor network connectivity happening some days in urban areas of Dodoma city posed a substantial hindrance to NMB agency access to digital credit platforms within the banking industry. This problem highlights the stark digital divide that still persists in many areas, where urban centers have access to cutting-edge technology, but the outskirts are left struggling with subpar network infrastructure” (Interviewee no 5, June 2023).

This finding implies that the bank is losing profit from consumers by failing to issue digital credit timely. This finding is similar to Smith *et al.*, (2019) who noted that network problems are a critical limiting factor hindering the digital credit platform's seamless operation in the banking industry. He mentioned these issues also include slow internet connectivity and unreliable data transmission, significantly disrupting the real-time assessment of borrower creditworthiness and the timely disbursement of loans, undermining the platform's effectiveness and customer experience. Moreover, Griffith-Jones *et al.*, (2020) added that these challenges increase operational costs and financial loss to various

banks. However, Griffith-Jones *et al.*, (2020:25) added that “financing digital infrastructure is particularly challenging, as it requires large initial investments, which tend to soak up most of a project’s costs”. Thus, there is a need to advocate for the government to partner with private sectors to improve network infrastructure for banking sector performance.

Limited Customer Awareness

Moreover, the findings show that customer awareness was another limiting factor. The study reveals that there is limited awareness of the use of digital platforms as an opportunity to acquire loans from financial institutions, particularly NMB Bank:

“...A Substantial portion of the bank customer remains uninformed about the benefits and importance of using digital credit platforms to expand their capital. This issue reflects a broader challenge in financial literacy, where individuals may not fully grasp how these digital tools can empower them economically...” (Interviewee no 3, June 2023).

This finding implies the need to orient customers on the benefits and use of digital credit platforms for easy lending purposes in the banking industry. As noted by Francis *et al.*, (2017) that “customers have little awareness of the products, fees, and terms of the loan” implying the need to create more awareness of digital credits among bank customers. The similar finding was noted by Agarwal *et al.* (2019), many potential borrowers remain unaware of the existence and benefits of these platforms, resulting in a lack of trust and reluctance to embrace digital lending solutions. Additionally, the study by Yao & Yang, (2022) emphasizes that the lack of customer knowledge about the terms, conditions, and risks associated with digital credit can lead to uninformed decisions, hindering the widespread adoption of these innovative financial services. This challenge calls for campaigns, seminars, and workshops about digital credit platforms. It also requires disclosure of terms and conditions by the digital credit providers such as interest rates, payment terms, and penalties associated with the service.

Lack of digital accessories

Also, the lack of digital accessories was highlighted as another limiting factor for digital credit platforms. The study discloses that most consumers lack ownership of modern digital accessories such as computers, Smartphones, iPads, and alike due to the low purchasing power of such items in the study area. Also, some claimed bundle expenses to facilitate the internet.

“...In Dodoma city majority of our agencies do not own digital accessories, or do not understand how to use those accessories, therefore this situation hinders them from accessing the digital credit platform services...” (Interviewee no 3, June 2023).

Also, another respondent added that:

“I feel that the lack of digital accessories, such as Smartphones and internet connectivity, is a significant limiting factor that hinders the growth of digital credit platforms in the banking industry...” (Interviewee no 1, June 2023).

These two quotations above imply that high prices on digital accessories as well as internet bundle prices have hindered the dull utilization of digital credit services. The findings supported by GSMA (2020) noted that a substantial portion of the global population still lacks access to smartphones and reliable internet services. Without these essential digital tools, individuals in underserved areas struggle to access and utilize digital credit services, impeding financial inclusion and the broader adoption of digital banking solutions (CGAP, 2018). This perception implies that consumer needs to have the necessary tools to access digital financial services. Therefore, financial institutions should support digital accessories to their consumer by integrating self-service options into their alternative channel devices. Furthermore, there is a need for digital literacy campaigns such as training and digital tutorials among bank customers to create awareness of digital accessories use for banking performance.

Cyber security

Additionally, other respondents added cyber security as another limiting factor. It was revealed that there is a great fear on the market due to hacking of digital devices by fraud stars where, they can trap credentials, and use them to borrow money digitally without the owner's concert.

“In the Tanzanian context, people still do not trust digital technology 100%. Most agencies do not trust the digital credit platform since they fear cybercrimes. Therefore, this situation hinders the banking industry in developing the digital credit platform...” (Interviewee no 4, June 2023).

This situation implies the need to safeguard sensitive information to ensure integrity during online banking practices. More protective measures such as (OTP) will send codes to the phone number and email of the device owner during credit application for confirmation purposes. As highlighted in a report by Akpan *et al.*, (2020) and Saeed *et al.*, (2023), cybercriminals continually evolve their tactics, targeting financial institutions with sophisticated attacks, including phishing and data breaches. Scholars argue that these threats not only jeopardize customer data but also, erode trust in digital credit services, discouraging potential users from engaging with these platforms (Luo *et al.*, 2019; Lee, 2021). Therefore, robust cyber security measures are imperative to mitigate these risks and foster a secure environment for digital credit in banking.

Conclusion

The study concludes that NMB digital credit platforms, digital credit accessibility, and time for loan processing have a positive and significant role in bank performance in the context of profit margin, in Dodoma City. These components are key determinants of the digital credit revolution at NMB for the bank's performance in the study area. However, the study concluded that insufficient access to networks; limited customer awareness; lack of digital accessories; cyber security; and low customer awareness, were the major limiting factors hindering NMB digital credit performance in the study area.

Recommendations

The study recommends maximizing NMB's digital credit platforms' use to enhance bank performance in Dodoma City and Tanzania in general. There is a need to embrace and diversify digital credit services; provide customer support services; and enhance the training programs for customer awareness creation. NMB can drive revenue growth and customer satisfaction by expanding the range of digital credit services and improving customer awareness and engagement. Furthermore, overcoming limiting factors involves collaborative efforts with regulators to establish supportive frameworks, prioritizing data security, enhancing digital infrastructure in underserved areas through partnerships, and developing innovative credit scoring mechanisms based on alternative data sources. These actions will help mitigate the challenges associated with digital credit platforms and ensure sustainable growth in the banking sector. The study also recommends collaborative efforts between government and private sectors in regulating cyber security to enhance banking performance.

Area for Further Research

The findings in this study are based on data collected from the NMB Agency located only in Dodoma City. Other regions in Tanzania, especially business cities that have high digital connectivity which encourages e-banking practices, have not been covered in this study. Therefore, this study provides opportunities for potential researchers and scholars to explore more areas to get a full picture of the digital credit revolution in the uncovered areas.

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